
CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK / TERMINOLOGICAL STRUCTURE

Glossary of Key Terms Related to Forced Expulsion through “Release” and the Configuration of Retained Criminal Status

A Terminological and Methodological Instrument
for the Structured Use of Concepts
within the Analytical and Conceptual Framework

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Methodological Glossary

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Systematization and formal clarification of key terms used in the Conceptual Framework and the Analytical Report on forced expulsion through “Release”.

Relation to the Conceptual Framework:

This glossary provides the structured terminology necessary for the consistent application and interpretation of the conceptual model Forced Expulsion through “Release”.

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Relation to the Analytical Report:

The glossary supports and clarifies the analytical findings presented in the report “Release Without Freedom: Forced Expulsion of Political Prisoners and Legal Vacuum in the Republic of Belarus” (20 December 2025) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18444848>.

Author:

Aleh Baradzin

Former political prisoner

Human rights analyst

Chair of the Supervisory Board of the Foundation for Belarusian Political Prisoners in Poland

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Introduction

This glossary systematizes and formalizes the key concepts used to describe the phenomenon of forced expulsion through “Release” as a distinct practice of the de facto removal of a person beyond the borders of a state, not encompassed by the classical legal categories of deportation, banishment, or voluntary migration.

The purpose of this document is to establish a terminological framework that enables accurate identification and analytical differentiation of this phenomenon.

This glossary has been developed on the basis of the analytical report and conceptual framework in which the practice of releasing individuals from places of deprivation of liberty with their subsequent de facto expulsion beyond the territory of the state has been examined in detail.

The empirical basis comprises 189 documentarily recorded cases of forced expulsion of political prisoners, carried out within three consecutive waves (14 persons - 21 June 2025; 52 persons - 11 September 2025; 123 persons - 13 December 2025), confirming the reproducibility and systemic character of the mechanism in question.

Within the documented practice, a single case of refusal to leave the territory of the state has been recorded, after which the individual was re-isolated and, since September 2025, no information has been available regarding his whereabouts or legal status, including whether he remains alive.

The definitions presented herein are the result of the generalization and systematization of the aforementioned material and should be considered in conjunction with the analytical report and the conceptual framework.

I. BASIC STRUCTURE OF THE MECHANISM

1. Forced Expulsion through “Release”

A state-implemented and reproducible practice in which the extraction of a person from places of deprivation of liberty is used as an element of a mechanism for their subsequent physical expulsion beyond the territory of the state, without:

- the legal completion of the criminal status;
- termination of the execution of the sentence;
- restoration of civil and political rights;
- formalization of expulsion in accordance with a procedure established by law.

The coercive character lies in the inevitability of return under state control in the event of refusal to leave.

Forced expulsion through “Release”, as a single reproducible mechanism, consists of the following stages:

- 1.1. Extraction from a place of deprivation of liberty
- 1.2. Retention of an unclosed criminal status
- 1.3. Short-term legal uncertainty
- 1.4. Transfer to the border
- 1.5. Physical expulsion
- 1.6. Negative alternative
- 1.7. External repression after departure

Explanation.

The Meaning of Using the Term “Release” in Quotation Marks

The use of the term “Release” in quotation marks indicates the divergence between release as the lawful termination of punishment and the factual extraction of a person from a place of deprivation of liberty followed by expulsion from the country while the criminal status remains unclosed.

An unclosed criminal status is understood as the absence of a lawful act terminating the sentence (pardon, amnesty, parole, review of the judgment, or any other ground provided by law). According to documented public testimonies of individuals who experienced expulsion, at the moment of extraction from places of deprivation of liberty and prior to crossing the state border, they were not provided with documents confirming the termination of the sentence. The use of quotation marks is necessary to distinguish legal release from the expulsion mechanism described herein.

1.1. Extraction from a place of deprivation of liberty

The **extraction from a place of deprivation of liberty** is the removal of a person from a place of deprivation of liberty prior to the completion of the imposed sentence and without the adoption of a legally prescribed act terminating the criminal status.

Extraction:

- is not accompanied by a pardon, amnesty, parole (conditional early release), or any other lawful termination of the sentence;
- is not confirmed by any document indicating the closure of the criminal status;
- is carried out as the initial stage of subsequent expulsion.

Extraction does not constitute release in the legal sense but represents a technical act of terminating physical detention within the institution while preserving the individual's criminal status.

1.2. Retention of an Uncompleted Criminal Status

The **retention of an uncompleted criminal status** refers to the absence of a legally prescribed act terminating the sentence (pardon, amnesty, conditional early release/parole, review of the judgment, or any other lawful ground) simultaneously with the extraction of a person from a place of deprivation of liberty.

As a result, the individual ceases to serve the sentence in fact; however, their criminal status continues to operate and is not considered completed.

1.3. Short-Term Legal Uncertainty

The **short-term legal uncertainty** is a state characterized by the absence of a formally documented termination of the sentence during the period between the extraction of a person from a place of deprivation of liberty and their actual expulsion.

1.4. Transfer to the Border

The **transfer to the border** is the movement of a person by state authorities to the state border following their extraction from a place of deprivation of liberty.

It is carried out without the possibility for the individual to independently choose their place of stay within the territory of the country and precedes physical expulsion.

1.5. Physical Expulsion

The **physical expulsion** is the compelled crossing of the state border following extraction from a place of deprivation of liberty and transfer to the border.

It is carried out without the lawful completion of the criminal status and without the possibility of safe stay within the territory of the country.

1.6. Negative Alternative

A **negative alternative** is a choice situation ("cross the border / refuse") in which refusal of expulsion leads to the removal of the person from the publicly verifiable legal space. One publicly confirmed case has been documented demonstrating the consequences of refusing to cross the state border after extraction from a place of deprivation of liberty. After being returned under the control of state authorities, the person effectively disappeared: there is no

verifiable information regarding his fate, including whether he is alive, and state authorities officially refused to disclose such information.

Refusal to leave does not constitute an admissible legal alternative.

1.7. Closed Isolation Outside Public Determinacy

The **closed isolation outside public determinacy** is a situation in which a person who has refused to leave is removed from the public legal space, and information regarding his or her whereabouts and legal status is absent.

In this state:

- the completion of the execution of the sentence is not confirmed;
- the continuation of the execution of the sentence in the established procedure is not confirmed;
- there is no possibility of public verification of the person's legal position.

Such a configuration excludes the verifiability of the execution of the sentence and removes the person from the regime of open legal procedure.

1.8. External Repression After Departure

The **external repression** is the continuation of the criminal status and the legal influence of the state after the physical expulsion of a person beyond the country's territory.

It is expressed in:

- the absence of lawful termination of the sentence;
- the impossibility of safe return;
- the persistence of the threat of renewed control or prosecution.

Expulsion does not terminate the repressive impact but transfers it beyond the territory of the state.

II. NORMATIVE MODEL AND ITS LIMITS

1. Normative Model of Release

The **normative model of release** is a legal construct under which release signifies the formally documented completion of a person's criminal status and the termination of the execution of the imposed sentence in accordance with a procedure established by law.

The normative model derives from:

- the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus;
- the Criminal Code and the Penal Enforcement legislation of the Republic of Belarus;
- the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ratified by the Republic of Belarus);
- other international human rights treaties binding upon the state.

According to this model, release from places of deprivation of liberty presupposes the simultaneous presence of the following legal elements:

- formal completion of the criminal status on the basis of an act provided for by law (completion of sentence, pardon, amnesty, parole, or another lawful ground);
- termination of the execution of the sentence in the established procedural form;
- legal certainty regarding the person's status after release;
- absence of the threat of arbitrary re-imposition of deprivation of liberty without a new lawful ground established by law;
- possibility of safe residence within the territory of the state.

2. Threshold of Applicability of the Normative Model of Release

The **threshold of applicability of the normative model of release** is the point at which the termination of deprivation of liberty does not coincide with the legal completion of the sentence and the person's criminal status.

Algorithmicity is established where the indicated elements are reproduced in the same structural and temporal sequence regardless of the specific features of an individual case.

The absence of an officially published regulation does not preclude algorithmicity if the sequence of actions is in fact reproduced according to an unchanged logic.

Algorithmicity distinguishes the described mechanism from isolated decisions or politically motivated exceptions and indicates the existence of a stable law-enforcement model.

3. Criteria for Identifying the Mechanism

The **criteria for identifying the mechanism** constitute a set of indicators, the simultaneous presence of which makes it possible to qualify a practice as forced expulsion through “Release”.

The minimum set of indicators includes:

- the absence of a legally prescribed act terminating the execution of the sentence;
- the continued validity of the judgment after the extraction of the person from a place of deprivation of liberty;
- transfer of the person to the state border carried out by state authorities or under their control;
- the absence of a lawful alternative to departure without return under state control or without loss of public determinacy of legal status.

The simultaneous presence of the indicated indicators distinguishes this mechanism from pardon, amnesty, parole, full completion of sentence, official deportation, and other procedures formalized by an independent decision on expulsion or lawful termination of the sentence.

4. Delineation from Lawful Forms of Release

The **delineation from lawful forms of release** consists in establishing the distinction between the described mechanism and:

- pardon;
- amnesty;
- parole;
- full completion of sentence;
- official deportation.

The criterion of delineation is the presence of a legally prescribed act terminating the execution of the sentence and the legally formalized completion of the criminal status.

Lawful forms of release presuppose the issuance of a corresponding legal act by a competent authority, its procedural formalization, and the possibility of judicial or other review of the legality of such a decision as provided by law.

In the absence of a legally prescribed act, the termination of detention does not constitute legal release.

IV. CONSEQUENCES AND VARIABLE STATES

1. Loss of Public Determinacy of Legal Status

The **loss of public determinacy of legal status** is a condition arising as a result of a person’s refusal to cross the state border after being removed from a place of deprivation of liberty, in which officially verifiable information regarding the person’s whereabouts, legal position, and fate is absent, making it impossible to verify the lawfulness of the execution of the sentence or the legal basis for further detention.

Indicators of loss of public determinacy include:

- absence of information regarding the person’s location;
 - absence of official confirmation of the continuation or termination of the execution of the sentence;
 - absence of an identifiable procedural decision subject to legal review;
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The normative model functions if, after release, the following are simultaneously ensured:

- termination of the execution of the sentence in accordance with the procedure established by law;
- irreversibility of the termination of isolation on the same legal grounds;
- legal certainty regarding the person's status;
- the possibility for the person to remain without the risk of repeated isolation.

The threshold arises where one or more of the following indicators are present:

- the execution of the sentence has not been legally completed;
- the person may be deprived of liberty again on the basis of a previously issued decision without the commission of a new offense.

In such a situation, release does not complete the sentence but signifies a change in the regime of control. Where the indicated elements are present, release may be used as a stage of forced expulsion.

3. Distortion of the Logic of Sentence Completion

The **distortion of the logic of sentence completion** is a situation in which the termination of deprivation of liberty is carried out while the judgment remains in force and coincides with the removal of the person beyond the jurisdiction of the state.

In such a configuration, the physical termination of isolation replaces the legal completion of the execution of the sentence.

The judgment continues to operate, the criminal-legal status of the person is not completed; however, instead of a lawful procedure for terminating the sentence, territorial removal takes place.

III. STRUCTURAL FEATURES OF THE MECHANISM

1. Reproducibility of the Mechanism

The **reproducibility of the mechanism** is the repetition of the same sequence of actions by state authorities in relation to different individuals while maintaining a unified legal construction: extraction from a place of deprivation of liberty → preservation of the validity of the sentence → transfer to the state border → physical expulsion.

Reproducibility is evidenced by:

- the coincidence of procedural stages;
- the absence of an act terminating the execution of the sentence;
- the preservation of the criminal status;
- compelled transfer to the state border.

The existence of a recurring structural pattern of actions makes it possible to qualify this practice as a stable law-enforcement mechanism rather than as an isolated episode.

2. Algorithmicity of the Procedure

Algorithmicity of the procedure is a stable and reproducible sequence of actions by state authorities in which each stage of forced expulsion through "Release" is logically and functionally connected to the subsequent stage.

The algorithm includes:

- extraction of a person from a place of deprivation of liberty prior to the completion of the execution of the sentence;
 - preservation of the validity of the judgment and the uncompleted criminal status;
 - absence of a lawful act terminating the sentence;
 - compelled transfer to the state border;
 - physical expulsion;
 - application of the negative alternative in the event of refusal to cross the border.
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- failure to provide verifiable information regarding the person's status within a period exceeding ordinary procedural notification time limits.

In such a configuration, the person temporarily falls outside the publicly verifiable legal space. The condition ceases upon the restoration of verifiable information concerning the person's legal status.

2. Temporary Removal from a Place of Deprivation of Liberty without Termination of the Judgment

Temporary removal from a place of deprivation of liberty without termination of the judgment is a condition in which a person leaves the institution executing the sentence; however, no formally adopted decision terminating, annulling, or modifying the criminal-legal status of the convicted person exists, and the legal force of the judgment remains in effect.

In this configuration:

- the judgment has not been annulled;
- the execution of the judgment has not been terminated;
- the person is not released from criminal liability;
- the status of a convicted person is preserved regardless of the person's actual place of stay.

Such a condition may be associated with health circumstances or other factors and is of a temporary nature until the execution of the judgment is modified or terminated.

V. FINAL PROVISION

Methodological Significance of the Glossary

The present glossary establishes the key concepts used to describe the practice of forced expulsion through "Release". Its purpose is to provide a unified and clear terminological framework for the accurate analysis of the relevant legal situations.

The glossary performs an auxiliary function in relation to the analytical report and the concept. It does not contain additional conclusions but serves as a tool for the correct application and further development of the proposed model in academic and legal work.